

Light and gas barrier properties of PLLA/metallic nanoparticles composite films

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Abstract

Herein we attempt to provide a deeper understanding on the influence of metal oxide nanoparticle incorporation on the gas transport properties of resulting polymer-based nanocomposites. Polylactide has been used as a model biodegradable material to develop nanocomposites containing 1 v/v % of TiO₂, SiO₂, Fe₂O₃ and Al₂O₃ spherical particles. These nanoparticles were characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM), X-ray and ζ -potential measurements. Thermal properties of nanocomposites were analyzed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), while scanning electron microscopy (SEM) has been used to correlate nanoparticle dispersion with both light and gas barrier properties. UV-Vis spectroscopy indicates a good UV-shielding performance of developed films. Water vapour transmission rate and oxygen permeability of nanocomposites were further determined and obtained results have been correlated to the effect of interactions between the incorporated nanoparticles and water/oxygen molecules. Taking into account that only 1 % of nanoparticles have been added, noticeable improvement of the barrier character of polylactide to water vapour, up to 18 %, and wet oxygen, up to 9 %, have been observed. Finally, Maxwell, Bruggeman, Böttcher and Higuchi models have been applied for our two-phase mixed matrix membranes to predict the permeability of dry oxygen. Overall, the experimental findings here shown provide better understanding towards the design of membrane devices based on biodegradable materials with tailored light and gas permeability for specific industrial applications.

Keywords: Poly(L-lactide); metallic nanoparticle, nanocomposites; gas transport; packaging.

1. Introduction

With the increasing government regulations and standards for the transition to a green economy, packaging, automotive and electrical/electronic industries demand the development of more environmentally sustainable products. Therefore, polymeric materials having high “carbon footprint” from petrochemical origin should be gradually replaced by products based on renewable feedstock [1–3]. With this growing awareness, during the last years an especial attention has been paid to the development of environmentally-friendly functional materials for food packing applications. Unfortunately, the chemical nature of conventional commodity plastics such as polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polystyrene (PS) or polypropylene (PP) prevents their degradation within a reasonable period by existing biological processes. In that sense, biodegradable polymers emerge as the preferential candidates for obtaining recyclable packaging with reduced size [4,5].

Poly lactide (PLA) is considered of prime interest to replace current petro-based polymers and is one of the biopolymers that shows higher potential for developing eco-friendly disposable packaging [6]. Due its initial high production costs PLA has been mainly used for high value applications such as the biomedical sector, although recently the fabrication of high molecular weight PLA has been achieved at affordable prices for its mass production [7]. PLA displays a good visible transparency of about 95% (determined as the light transmission in the 540-560 nm range (ASTMD1746-03)) [8], environmentally friendly character, degradability in biological environment into non-toxic components and a thermoplastic-type processability [6,9]. In regard to the amorphous isomer, the semicrystalline isomeric form of poly (L-lactide) (PLLA) provides more versatility for packaging applications due to its easily tuneable degradability, phase-structure and physico-mechanical properties [6,10,11].

In order to make it competitive with currently used polymers for packaging applications, both light and gas barrier properties of PLLA need to be improved [12,13]. This would enable the fabrication of parts that protect light and gas sensitive foods, extending the shelf-life and improving the food quality. For example, ultraviolet (UV) shielding of PLLA remains lower than that of PET, which blocks UV-C and UV-B wavelengths ($\lambda < 315$ nm) [6]. This issue could be overcome through the addition of UV absorbing additives. Concerning to gas barrier properties, it is generally accepted that the introduction of nonporous fillers reduces the permeability of the bulk material *via* two concomitant effects. On the one hand these fillers create a tortuous diffusion path for the penetrants through the membrane which decreases the diffusion parameter, while on the other hand the amount of the material through which molecules permeate is decreased at the same time that the available free volume for the penetrant changes, modifying the solubility parameter [14–16]. Surprisingly, several authors have observed enhanced gas permeability when some polymers are reinforced with inorganic nanoparticles [17,18]. This behaviour, which contradicts the assumptions arising from the classical composite theory has been attributed to the formation of an extra free volume around the nanoparticle-matrix interface which increases the diffusion coefficients of gases [18].

For developing efficient packaging materials, besides of obtaining good UV and gas barrier properties, usually antimicrobial agents are needed to inhibit the growth of food-born microorganism during the storage of the food [19]. These agents include but are not limited to metals like copper, gold, silver and zinc [20]. Nonetheless, in view to fabricate cheap and scalable materials, metal oxide nanoparticles are gaining interest due to their low cost, wide availability and good physico-chemical properties. Several metal oxides have been already mixed with polymers in order to upgrade their properties. For example, to date PLA/TiO₂ nanocomposites have mainly devoted to photo-degradability studies [21], crystallization kinetics [22] and drug delivery systems [23]. Another interesting material to be considered in that sense is silica (SiO₂), which apart from being abundant in the nature, is cheap and has an easily functionalizable surface [24]. Silica nanoparticles have been proven to effectively increase the tensile strength and thermal stability of PLLA [25], although scarce

works have been devoted to study the barrier properties of biopolymers reinforced with SiO₂ nanoparticles. On the other hand, iron (III) oxide (Fe₂O₃) nanoparticles have attracted attention because of their superparamagnetic properties [26], although no extensive works have been carried out in understanding the gas barrier properties of polymer nanocomposites reinforced with Fe₂O₃. Alumina (Al₂O₃) nanoparticles have been extensively used to develop polymer nanocomposites [27]. These materials are cheap and can improve the mechanical performance of their hosting matrix [28], besides of displaying high chemical and thermal stability and forming nearly transparent films to the naked eye [29].

In this work we aim to provide further understanding how the incorporation of different spherical metallic nanoparticles (TiO₂, SiO₂, Fe₂O₃ and Al₂O₃) with similar size influences gas transport of resulting materials. To discuss the role of the nanofiller nature, films with homogeneously distributed nanoparticles were prepared for a fixed concentration of inorganic matter by solvent-precipitation followed by compression moulding. The light transmission in the ultraviolet-visible spectral region is as well investigated to provide further data on the barrier properties. The morphology of obtained films and their thermal and mechanical properties are further investigated. The experimental data shown in this work would allow the design of membrane devices with tailored gas and light permeability for specific applications.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Starting materials

PLLA with a number-average molecular weight (M_n) of 100.000 g·mol⁻¹ and a polydispersity index (M_w/M_n) of 1.85 was supplied by Purac Biochem (The Netherlands). Metal oxide nanoparticles, namely titanium dioxide (TiO₂), silicon dioxide (SiO₂), aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃) and ferric oxide (Fe₂O₃), have been purchased by L'Urederra technological centre (Spain).

2.2. Sample preparation

Samples have been prepared by solvent-precipitation followed by compression moulding. Metal oxide nanoparticles were homogeneously dispersed in chloroform (CHCl₃) via mild-sonication (20% output for 5 minutes, Vibra-Cell™ CV 334) and they were added to previously dissolved PLLA to yield nanoparticle concentrations of 1 v/v % (see Table 1). Another sonication step (10 minutes) has been applied to dispersions before precipitating them in an excess of cold methanol. After vacuum drying (48 h at 60 °C), films with a thickness of ~200 μm were fabricated by compression moulding at 190 °C for 3 minutes under a pressure of 150 MPa. Subsequently, films were water quenched to avoid the development of large crystalline fractions. Membranes for water vapour measurements were prepared by compression moulding at 190 °C for 4 minutes and 6 MPa. The membranes for water vapour and oxygen measurements were dried in vacuum at room temperature for at least one week and the thickness of the membranes is between 70-135 μm.

Table 1. The respective density values of employed nanoparticles and their corresponding volume concentration within the nanocomposite.

	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃
ρ (g/cm ³)	2.65	4.24	3.95	5.25
v/v %	1	1	1	1
wt. %	2.1	3.31	3.09	4.07

2.3. Morphological characterization

Raw nanoparticles were examined by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a Philips CM120 Biofilter apparatus with STEM module at an acceleration voltage of 120 kV. Cryofractured surfaces of nanocomposites have been analyzed in a Hitachi S-4800 field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) at an acceleration voltage of 5 kV. Surfaces were chromium-coated in a Quorum Q150T ES turbo-pumped sputter coater (5 nm thick coating).

2.4. Wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD)

Wide angle X-ray diffraction (WAXD) has been conducted to determine the crystalline structure of nanoparticles. X-ray powder diffraction patterns were collected in a PHILIPS X'PERT PRO automatic diffractometer in theta-theta configuration, secondary monochromator with Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) and a PIXcel solid state detector. The sample was mounted on a zero background silicon wafer fixed in a generic sample holder. Data were collected from 20 to 75° 2 θ (step size = 0.026).

2.5. Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) has been used to determine the zeta potential of metallic nanoparticles. Experiments were performed on a Zetasizer Nano S from Malvern Instruments. Nanoparticles were dispersed in Mili-Q water at 0.1 wt. % and ultrasonicated for 2 minutes at room temperature. Measurements were made at 25 °C using disposable folded capillary cells (DTS1070). Smoluchowski's theory was used for zeta-potential determination. Nanoparticle refractive indexes were set as 2.40 for Fe₂O₃, 1.62 for Al₂O₃, 1.54 for SiO₂ and 2.41 for TiO₂.

2.6. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

The thermal behaviour of nanocomposites was determined using a Mettler Toledo DSC 822e calorimeter under N₂ atmosphere (30 ml/min). Samples of 8 mg were sealed in an aluminium pan, heated from 0 °C to 200 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min in order to determine thermal transitions (T_g and T_m). Taking into account that thermal properties of samples as prepared have to be consider in relation to the permeation processes, only first scan was measured. The crystalline fraction X_c (%) corresponding to PLLA crystallization was determined as [30]:

$$X_c (\%) \square \frac{\Delta H_f - \Delta H_c}{\Delta H_f^0 \cdot W_m} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

where ΔH_f and ΔH_c are the enthalpy of fusion and cold crystallization of the samples respectively and W_m is the PLLA matrix weight fraction ($\Delta H_f^0 = 106 \text{ J/g}$ was taken as the heat of fusion of an infinitely thick PLLA crystal [31]).

2.7. UV-Vis spectroscopy

UV-Vis transmission spectra were recorded with a Shimadzu MultiSpec-1501 spectrophotometer. Total transmittance experiments have been analyzed in the range of 190 to 800 nm with a sampling interval of 1nm and 25 accumulations.

2.8. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA)

Thermodegradative behaviour of PLLA/metallic nanoparticle films was analyzed by thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA) using a METTLER TOLEDO 822e instrument. Samples were placed into alumina pans and were heated from room temperature to 500°C at 10°C/min under a nitrogen flux of 50 ml/min.

2.9. Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA)

Dynamic Mechanic Analysis (DMA) was performed on a DMA/SDTA861 analyzer (Mettler-Toledo) in tensile mode. 200 µm thick films (4 x 5.5 mm) were cut from compression-moulded sheets and were submitted to a force amplitude of 1 N at a frequency of 1 Hz. Curves displaying storage modulus (E') and the energy loss ($\tan \delta$) were recorded in the 0-110 °C range at a heating rate of 3 °C/min.

2.10. Gas barrier measurements

Water vapour transmission rate has been measured employing a permeation cell at 25 °C according to ASTM E96-95. The permeation cell is a small container made of polytetrafluoroethylene that is partially filled with water and a polymer membrane sealing its top. The weight loss is measured in a Sartorius BP 210 D balance with 10^{-5} g readability and recorded in a computer for data treatment. The permeability values shown are the average of at least 4 measurements.

Oxygen permeability has been determined with a Mocon Ox-tran model 2/21 MH equipment according to ASTM standard D3985-10 and ISO 15105-1.2. Measurements were carried out at 23 °C, 1 atm and 0 and 50 % relative humidity. More details about the permeation cells and experimental methods are reported in previous works [32,33]. The permeability values shown are the average of at least 2 measurements.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of nanoparticles

Transmission electron microscopy was carried out to determine the shape and size of reinforcing metallic nanoparticles. TEM micrographs in Fig. 1 show that all nanoparticles present a nanometric spherical shape with diameters of 13.4 ± 4.4 , 11.6 ± 4.3 , 19 ± 9.1 and 28.8 ± 9.9 nm for SiO₂, TiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ respectively (statistics based on count of 50 particles; see Fig. S1 for nanoparticle length-distribution). Additionally, wide angle X ray diffraction (WAXD) patterns of nanoparticles in Fig. S2 show featured reflections corresponding to amorphous silica (silica glass) for SiO₂, a mixture of anatase and rutile phases for TiO₂ (JCPDS reference no. 01-073-1764 and 01-078-1510 respectively) [34], cubic γ -alumina structure (JCPDS reference no. 00-010-0425) [35] and the cubic spinel structured maghemite for Fe₂O₃ (JCPDS reference no. 00-024-0081). The γ -Fe₂O₃ phase is a magnetic transition metal oxide where O atoms form a fcc close-packed structure [36].

Fig. 1. Representative transmission electron microscopy (TEM) image of metallic nanoparticles at 230.000x.

Not only the size, shape and chemistry of the nanoparticle influence the resulting physico-chemical properties of NPs, but also their local environment. This nanoenvironment around the NPs differs from the bulk and determines the interaction of the nanoparticle with its surrounding medium [37]. It is therefore expected that, apart from the dispersion of NPs within the hosting PLLA, the permeability behaviour in these nanocomposites could be as well affected by the surface charge of nanoparticles because this charge affect the interaction of NPs with the permeant molecules. Table 2 shows the average zeta potential (ζ -potential) values of nanoparticles when dispersed in water at 25 °C, while Fig. S3 depicts obtained ζ -potential distribution graphs. TiO₂ presents a neutral surface charges as shown by the measured ζ -potential of -0.9 ± 5.8 mV, while Al₂O₃ surfaces are positively charged (35.7 ± 7.5 mV) and both SiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ are negatively charged (ζ -potential smaller than -35 mV). Intense charges on the nanoparticle surfaces leads to repulsive forces between them, allowing stable dispersions. Therefore, when NPs present not net charge, as in the case of TiO₂, nanoparticles may get close, forming larges aggregates when mixed with a hosting matrix. On the contrary, as a result of their highly charged surfaces (an absolute value of ζ -potential above 30 mV is commonly used to indicate solution stability), Al₂O₃, SiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ would keep them highly dispersed within the PLLA matrix [38].

Table 2. Measured zeta potential of nanoparticles in water at 25 °C.

	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃
Zeta potential (mV)	-37.5 ± 4.5	-0.9 ± 5.8	35.7 ± 7.5	-41.6 ± 6.4

3.2. Thermal characterization

Differential scanning calorimetric measurements have been carried out to characterize the glass transition temperature and crystallinity level of the samples since these properties may affect the permeability of the resulting films. Accordingly, Table 3 depicts the glass transition temperature (T_g),

melting temperature (T_m), crystallinity degree (X_c) and crystallization half time ($t_{1/2}$) of nanocomposites when crystallized from the melt at 120 °C (see Fig. S4 for DSC heating traces).

Table 3. Thermal properties of nanocomposite films as obtained from DSC.

	T_g (°C)	T_m (°C)	X_c (%)	$t_{1/2}$ (min)
Neat PLLA	58.6	174.5	11.9	3.16
PLLA/SiO ₂	60.7	175.3	15.9	1.03
PLLA/TiO ₂	58.1	174.5	18.2	0.94
PLLA/Al ₂ O ₃	61.2	175.8	15.9	0.89
PLLA/Fe ₂ O ₃	59.4	174.4	16.1	0.83

It is observed that the addition of nanoparticles slightly increases the glass transition temperature, except for TiO₂ in which a similar value to PLLA is obtained, indicating that SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles restrict the segmental motion of PLLA chains [8,39]. The dispersion of the nanoparticles plays a major role in the restriction of the mobility being SiO₂ and Al₂O₃, which are isotropically dispersed (this will be shown later in SEM micrographs), the most effective as constraining elements. In the melting temperature there are not great changes with the addition of nanoparticles except for SiO₂ and Al₂O₃, in which a slight increase is observed. On the other hand the crystallinity level of PLLA increases considerably, between 34-53 %, with the addition of nanoparticles being higher for SiO₂ and Al₂O₃. Because of its stereoregularity, PLLA chains are able to be organized into ordered domains during their cooling from the melt to temperatures below T_g [8,11]. According to Table 3, the amount of crystallized fraction (X_c) increases with nanoparticle addition as commonly found in polymer nanocomposites. This effect is ascribed to a nucleating behaviour provided by the introduced nanoparticle surfaces, which results in faster crystallization kinetics because polymer chains are able to grow from predetermined nuclei (metallic nanoparticles), reaching the completion of crystallization process faster when comparing with neat polymer [8,22]. The crystallization half time, $t_{1/2}$, that describes the crystallization kinetics of the material is greatly reduced with the addition of nanoparticles being at least three times lower for the nanocomposites. Therefore the increase found in the crystallinity level as well as the reduction in $t_{1/2}$ indicates that the nanoparticles act as effective nucleating agents. Similar behaviour has been observed for other nanocomposites such as PLLA/ZnO [8], Nylon 6/ZnO [40] and PP/CaCO₃ [41], among others.

To ensure that obtained nanocomposite films do not suffer any apparent thermodegradation process during their fabrication process, the thermodegradative behaviour of PLLA/metallic nanoparticle films was analyzed by thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA). As shown in Fig. S5 and Table 1, nanoparticle addition decreases the onset of thermodegradation process (determined by the first 5 % of weight loss) from 338.5 °C for neat PLLA to 324.7 °C for its Al₂O₃ nanocomposite. This decreased thermal stability is not enough to induce thermally-activated chain-scission events in PLLA, since the onset of thermal degradation remains 135 °C above the processing temperature. Therefore, these results prove that the nanocomposite films here fabricated are suitable for melt-processing techniques

3.3. Morphological and mechanical characterization of nanocomposites

It is known that the macroscopic properties of nanocomposites are strongly related to the nanoparticle dispersion within the hosting matrix. In this sense, an homogeneous dispersion of nanoparticles within their hosting matrix is required in order to successfully improve the barrier performance of nanocomposite films [42,43]. Fig. 2 depicts scanning electron microscopy cross-section images of 1 v/v % PLLA nanocomposites. It is observed that SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ are isotropically well-dispersed within their hosting matrix, while TiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ form large aggregates of about

100-150 nm as a result of entanglements between adjacent nanoparticles. It should be noted that Fe_2O_3 tend to aggregate when they are mixed into polymeric matrices as a result of their magnetic properties [36]. This agglomeration results in a structure characteristic of microcomposites rather than nanocomposites, where large material areas remain free from nanoparticles. From this result, it could be thus expected that PLLA/ SiO_2 and PLLA/ Al_2O_3 would present the best barrier performances because of the increased tortuosity imposed by the achieved homogeneous structure. This hypothesis will be discussed later.

Fig. 2. FE-SEM micrographs of cryogenically fractured surfaces obtained at a magnification of 20.000X.

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) has been carried out to analyze the mechanical properties of nanocomposite films. As depicted in Fig. S6, glass transition temperature of nanocomposites (determined as the maximum $\tan \delta$) increases by 3-4 °C in the presence of metallic nanoparticles, while $\tan \delta$ values decrease from 2.44 to ~ 2.2 upon nanoparticle addition. This concomitant T_g increase and $\tan \delta$ decrease agrees well with above-mentioned DSC results and could be related to a chain confinement effect in which the chain mobility is restricted at nanoparticle surfaces [8,11].

3.4. Surface hydrophobicity

It is well established that controlling the behaviour of water at the interfaces is a key parameter in order to tune the resulting physical properties of materials [44–46]. In this context, static water contact angle (WCA) of nanocomposites surface has been measured using the sessile drop method and the representative images of a water drop at the film surface are shown in Fig. 3. It is seen that the surface hydrophobicity does not substantially change upon nanoparticle addition. While neat PLLA presents a rather hydrophobic nature as denoted by the WCA of $81^\circ \pm 2$ [8], the hydrophobicity of PLLA/ TiO_2 is slightly increased as denoted by the achieved WCA of $83^\circ \pm 2$. On the contrary, when PLLA is reinforced with SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 , the hydrophilicity of nanocomposite films increases to some extent (WCA of $76^\circ \pm 4$, $79^\circ \pm 2$ and $80^\circ \pm 3$ respectively), specially for PLLA/ SiO_2 nanocomposite. Taking into account that the permeability P , is defined as the product of diffusivity (D) and solubility (S) [47], it is *a priori* expected that the water vapour permeability of films would be markedly reduced upon the addition of TiO_2 since, besides of the diffusivity reduction *via* tortuosity increase, these nanoparticles reduce the water-affinity of the film, reducing the solubility of H_2O molecules within the nanocomposite. When permeability results will

be discussed we will corroborate if the increased hydrophilicity of PLLA/SiO₂ leads to a larger water-solubility, therefore affecting also to the H₂O permeability.

Fig. 3. Representative images of a water drop at the surface of neat PLLA and nanocomposite films. Average water contact angle values and their corresponding standard deviation are shown.

3.5. UV-Vis shielding

It is widely accepted that the high transparency of PLLA to ultraviolet (UV) light is an issue that needs to be overcome in order to use this polymer for packaging applications. This UV-transparency markedly affects the food quality since the lipids, flavours, vitamins and pigments undergo degradation reactions when exposed to light [48]. In this framework, the ideal UV-blocking element should present a transmittance of 0 % at wavelengths below 400 nm and a complete transparency (identified as a transmittance of 100 %) at wavelengths exceeding 400 nm. It is therefore expected that the addition of nanoparticles into PLLA having a filled valence band and an empty conduction band may improve the UV-barrier properties of the hosting matrix [49]. Accordingly, light barrier properties of nanocomposite films have been evaluated by UV-Vis transmittance spectroscopy in the 200-800 nm range. It is observed in Fig. 4 that PLLA has a high light transparency over the whole studied range, while the relative number of photons that pass through the film is reduced upon nanoparticle loading. As a consequence, the presence of 1 v/v % decreases the amount of transmitted UV light (at a wavelength of 300 nm) from 89 % for neat PLLA to 11-42 % for the nanocomposite counterparts, similarly to that obtained for PLLA/ZnO nanocomposites [8]. Moreover, the transparency of nanocomposites determined according to the ASTM D1746-03 standard remains barely unchanged at ~97 % for PLLA/SiO₂ and PLLA/Al₂O₃ nanocomposites, while the addition of TiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ decreases the film transparency to 87 and 78 % respectively. This lower transparency for PLLA/TiO₂ and PLLA/Fe₂O₃ systems could be ascribed to their stronger light absorbing behaviour as well as to the produced Rayleigh scattering upon particle aggregation, which induces an increased light loss as particle size increases [50]. These results agree well with reported FE-SEM dispersion studies, where the more homogeneous nanoparticle dispersions were achieved for PLLA/SiO₂ and PLLA/Al₂O₃ nanocomposites.

Fig. 4. UV-Vis transmittance spectra of untreated metallic nanoparticles.

3.6. Water vapour permeability

The determination of water vapour permeability is of great interest since it plays a major role in the preservation and shelf life of food. In Fig. 5 the data obtained for PLLA and its nanocomposites are depicted (see Table S2 for permeability coefficients). Neat PLLA shows a water vapour transmission rate (WVTR) of 8.7 g mm/m² day, which is a high value comparing to the data of literature that is between 1.2-4.6 g mm/m² day [51, 52]. The addition of TiO₂ nanoparticles reduces greatly the permeability, 18 %, while both Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ induce also a substantial reduction, 13 and 16 %, respectively, with using only a 1 % v/v of nanoparticles in all the cases. The less efficient nanoparticle to reduce the water vapour permeability is SiO₂, in which an improvement of only 4 % has been observed.

Fig. 5. Water vapour transmission rate (WVTR) of neat PLLA and its nanocomposites.

As it has been mentioned in the introduction, many factors could affect to permeability in such type of heterogeneous materials as the tortuosity due to the presence and dispersion of nanoparticles

as well as the impenetrable crystalline regions, the interphase characteristics, the generation of additional free volume and the interactions involved between all the components, among others. In this case, the largest permeability decrease with TiO_2 could be ascribed to the lowest particle diameter, which would lead to a more tortuous pathway reducing the diffusion coefficient and therefore the permeability [53, 54]. Also, PLLA/ TiO_2 presents the highest crystallinity value, which would reduce permeability since crystalline regions are considered impermeable [55]. However, SEM micrographs have shown that TiO_2 presents large aggregates. For other three penetrants, the particle size of SiO_2 is slightly higher than TiO_2 , its dispersion better, being its crystallinity similar to Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 . Therefore it seems that other factor is playing the most important role. Actually, this behaviour may arise from the difference on particle-water interactions.

In this sense, focusing to zeta potential values, TiO_2 presents a neutral surface while other penetrants have large positive value, as Al_2O_3 , or negative ones, as occurs in SiO_2 and Fe_2O_3 cases. Taking into account the amphoteric character of water, both negative and positive surface charges could easily interact strongly with water molecules increasing solubility and even making easier a diffusion pathway. However, also the opposite behaviour would occur; due to that interactions water molecules could be adsorbed at specified sites and then become immobilized leading to a reduction of the global permeation process. Thus, these effects would balance partially or even totally the aforementioned factors.

In this sense, the nanocomposite containing TiO_2 is the most hydrophobic which could lead to a reduction of the solubility decreasing the permeability as well as to make easier that water would form clusters, which also lead to a diffusion coefficient decrease [56]. On the other hand, the addition of SiO_2 increases the hydrophilicity. This fact suggests that immobilization of the water molecules would be less effective. Indeed, interactions of water with hydrophilic sites of the nanoparticles could enhance successive jumps between such types of sites providing a quicker diffusion pathway [57]. We will discuss this issue later. Curiously in literature the addition of TiO_2 does not improve the permeability for filler contents below 5%, which can be due to the higher diameter of the nanoparticles [58].

3.7. Oxygen permeability

Oxygen can provoke changes in the food quality and safety, such as oxidative reactions and the growth of aerobic microorganisms, so is interesting to know the permeability to this penetrant. In addition, the presence of water can strongly affect the permeation of oxygen. Therefore, as shown in Fig. 6 in this work the oxygen permeability has been determined under dry conditions and at 50% relative humidity (see Table S1 for permeability coefficients).

Fig. 6. Oxygen permeability coefficients of neat PLLA and its nanocomposites in dry and 50 % humidity conditions.

The permeability of PLLA for dry oxygen has been determined to be 0.45 Barrer, a higher value than those reported in literature that are in the range of 0.14-0.39 Barrer [59, 60]. Taking into account that the measured WVTR for pure PLLA is also higher than reported values, it would be deduced that additional free volume had been generated in our samples. For nanocomposites two different trends could be observed: SiO₂ and TiO₂ improve the barrier character of PLLA to oxygen while Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ increase the permeability. Increase of oxygen permeability in materials with nanoparticles with low aspect ratio, as occurs in our samples, has been also obtained using computing modelling [61]. In any case, changes induced by the nanoparticles in the oxygen permeability coefficient are quite small (below 5% in all the cases). Taking into account these results and the less interacting character of the oxygen when comparing with water, it would be deduced that morphological features as both size and dispersion of nanoparticles, free volume holes, among others, do not play the most important role in the permeation process in our samples, as water vapour WVTR results also suggest. It should be noticed that the chemical nature of the penetrants is very different. While water molecules can interact strongly through hydrogen bonds or dipole-dipole interactions, oxygen can only form weak van der Waals bonds. Thus, the differences observed for water vapour could be more related with other factors as the interaction balance between penetrant, polymer matrix and nanoparticles as well as the nanoparticle surface charge.

In order to clarify these points, we have measured the oxygen permeability coefficient at 50% relative humidity (RH). Substantial differences in the oxygen permeability coefficient for the four nanocomposites have been observed when is measured in presence of water against to those measured for dry oxygen. Again, TiO₂ results the most effective nanoparticle to improve the wet oxygen barrier properties, 9 %, Fe₂O₃ also reduces the permeability a 5 % while it is maintain constant with Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ worsens. However, it must be reminded that in the case of Al₂O₃ dry oxygen permeability coefficient was superior to pure PLLA, 7 %. Thus, the presence of water in the oxygen permeability affects more pronouncedly PLLA/Al₂O₃ nanocomposite than pure PLLA. But, the most interesting result is that each metallic oxide effect in the permeability of oxygen at 50 % HR is very similar to those observed with water vapour in terms of their effectiveness, both qualitatively and quantitatively. Even the decrease of oxygen permeability in presence of water has been related to the competition of both penetrants to fill the free volume holes [62, 63], taking into account the measured magnitudes both zero potential and hydrophobicity could be useful in order to explain permeability results for both water vapour and oxygen at 50 % RH. In relation to these magnitudes

TiO₂ becomes more hydrophobic the nanocomposite surface while the nanoparticles has a neutral surface charge, the other three nanoparticles becomes more hydrophilic and both SiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ offers negative surface charges while the surface charge for Al₂O₃ is positive.

Analysing the results, it can be deduced that in presence of water molecules interactions take the most preponderant factor in the permeation process in our PLLA/metallic nanoparticles material and both film surface and nanoparticle surface charges provoke different behaviours. Spite of the formation of interactions would induce larger water solubility; the overall permeability decrease suggests that diffusion process is also strongly affected. Starting with most effective metallic oxide, TiO₂, the major hydrophobic character of the surface would make easier that water molecules form clusters leading to their immobilization. In the other three cases, sample surfaces become more hydrophilic, but while both Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ also cause a substantial reduction of permeability SiO₂ only produces a slight decrease of the WVTR and even an increase of oxygen permeability at 50 % HR when is compared to the value obtained for dry oxygen. However, we have to remind that the zeta potential of both Fe₂O₃ and SiO₂ present negative charges whereas Al₂O₃ have positive ones. Thus, it seems that the type of surface charges has not a crucial role and their different behaviour must be explained based on other factors.

As mentioned before, hydrophilicity could induce immobilization of the adsorbed water molecules, which in turn would provoke the reduction of diffusion process. However, as stated above, the opposite behaviour could be also induced due to that interactions make easier successive jumps providing a quicker diffusion pathway [63]. Taking into account that the reduction of water vapour WVTR in PLLA/SiO₂ sample is inferior to those observed for all the three cases and even the increase of the oxygen permeability coefficient at 50% HR it could be considered that the diffusion pathway formation is more relevant in PLLA/SiO₂ sample. Perhaps the better dispersion observed for PLLA/SiO₂ would enable the formation of preferential channels.

In conclusion, in our opinion the behaviour of both water vapour and wet oxygen differs to dry oxygen permeability due to the stronger interactions between the nanoparticle surfaces and water. These interactions must increase water solubility but also could lead to a partial immobilization of water molecules on the nanoparticle surfaces decreasing its permeability as well as affecting to the oxygen one due to the aforementioned competition [62,63]. However, the presence of water molecules at the surfaces could also lead to plasticization behaviour [64]. This fact as well as the better dispersion of SiO₂ nanoparticles would explain its different trend respect to the other three studied nanoparticles. Anyway, taking into account that differences between four studied materials are not so large, this hypothesis should be taken with caution because the results should be considered as a delicate balance between all the involved factors than in absolute terms.

3.8. Permeability prediction

Several approaches have been made in literature in order to predict different properties of nanocomposites such as mechanical properties, electric conductivity and permeability. Among the wide number of models available for two-phase mixed matrix membranes in this work Maxwell, Bruggeman, Böttcher and Higuchi models have been applied [65]. For the theoretical determination of the permeability dry oxygen has been chosen since it is more appropriate than water due to its chemical nature. All the cited models predict a value of 0.44. In this case with the simplest model a good result is obtained and the other models that take into account different assumptions about the dispersed phase and matrix, such as the size, shape, orientation, among others, are not very relevant. This result strengthens the aforementioned comment of the dry permeability results.

The values obtained are similar to that of TiO₂ nanocomposite in which a slight improvement in barrier character to oxygen is found. Applied models do not take into account the chemical nature

and interactions of the nanoparticles therefore it is not possible to accurately predict the permeability of each nanocomposite.

4. Conclusions

In this work we aim to provide further understanding how the incorporation of different spherical metallic nanoparticles influences gas transport of resulting materials. Samples containing 1 v/v % of SiO₂, TiO₂, Fe₂O₃ and Al₂O₃ have been fabricated by solvent-precipitation followed by compression moulding. DSC results showed faster crystallization kinetics for all the nanocomposites as a result of the nucleating effect of incorporated nanoparticles. Morphological analysis reveals a homogeneous distribution of SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ within the hosting PLLA matrix, while TiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ form large aggregates of about 100-150 nm as a result of entanglements between adjacent nanoparticles. It is observed that the presence of nanoparticles limits the transmitted UV light from 89 % for neat PLLA to 11-42 % for the nanocomposite counterparts, while the visible transparency is kept above 80 %.

It is observed that the addition of all the nanoparticles into PLLA markedly reduce the water vapour permeability of the resulting nanocomposites, up to 18 %, while no remarkable permeability changes are observed when dry oxygen is used as a permeant molecule. Moreover, permeability of wet oxygen has been also reduced up to 9 %. This different behaviour has been interpreted in terms of the effect of interactions between the nanoparticles and water molecules. These interactions should lead to larger solubility but permeability results suggests that water molecules become more immobilized than in pure PLLA. Differences between studied nanoparticles have been ascribed to the major hydrophobicity in the case of TiO₂ and the generation of a quicker diffusion pathway in the SiO₂ case. All the checked models for the theoretical determination of the permeability through two-phase mixed matrix membranes predicted a value of 0.44 Barrer for dry oxygen, which is similar to the obtained for PLLA/TiO₂, indicating a small relevance of the morphological factors related to the morphology (size, shape and orientation) of our samples. Overall, the experimental data shown in this work would allow the design of membrane devices with tailored gas and light permeability for specific applications.

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